

Impact of Prosecution of Offenders on the Fight Against Human Trafficking in Nigeria

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Abstract

The fight against trafficking in person requires a multi-dimensional approach considering the clandestine and lucrative nature of this heinous crime. Pragmatic among these approaches is the effective prosecution of offenders to deter others from engaging in the criminal act of exploiting others for illegal gains. The focus of this paper is on the impact of prosecution of offenders on the fight against trafficking in persons in Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study are to: investigate the effect of prompt investigation, prosecution, and conviction of human trafficking offenders on the fight against human trafficking in Nigeria and to determine the effect of severity of punishment for trafficking in persons on the fight against human trafficking in Nigeria. The study is anchored on the criminal deterrent theory as posited by Beccaria, Bentham, and Hobbs that celerity, certainty, and severity of punishment have the propensity in determining behavior towards crime. The study used staff from selected departments in NAPTIP and selected NGOs registered with NAPTIP as the population of the study, and the data collected from the survey was analyzed with multiple linear regression. Findings from the study clearly show a significant effect of prompt arrest, prosecution, and conviction of human trafficking offenders on the fight against human trafficking in Nigeria. The result of the finding also highlights the crucial role of severity of punishment in the fight against human trafficking in Nigeria. It is recommended that judicial officers and prosecutors should be adequately protected from the offenders and their criminal gang to safeguard them from being attacked by the human trafficking criminal ring. NAPTIP should launch a nationwide awareness campaign to educate the public about human trafficking and highlight successful prosecution cases to demonstrate the effectiveness of the legal system in combating trafficking.

Keywords: Trafficking in persons, Human traffic offenders, Palermo protocol.

Word count: 292

1. Introduction

One of the pragmatic approaches in the effort to combat trafficking in persons is the prosecution of human traffic offenders. This becomes imperative considering the compelling consequences the ferocious activities of human trafficking have on the individual victims and society. Individual victims are abused with an attendant debilitating psychological/mental health and economic catastrophe. Victims are exposed to criminalization by the state, and their rights are completely subjugated or brazenly abused. The economic potentials of society are also disrupted and distorted by the activities of this criminal gang. Diplomatic tension among states is heightened because of immigration concerns arising from victims' rights and prosecution of offenders. Human trafficking also robs families of their loved ones and proceeds from this illicit trade can be used as a source of funds to destabilize national security.

In recognition of the calamitous effect this heinous crime of trafficking in person has on individuals and society, the Palermo protocol to prevent, suppress, and punish trafficking in persons, especially women and children, provided in Article 5 for the criminalization of any act established by national legislation of state parties as trafficking in person. This implies state parties to the protocol must strengthen their criminal justice system to adequately prosecute acts of trafficking in persons. Thus, the effectiveness of prosecution is better demonstrated by the severity, promptness, and certainty of the judicial system to prosecute offenders.

As a state party to the Palermo Protocol, the Nigerian government, through the Trafficking in Persons (Prohibition) Enforcement of Administration Act 2015 (as amended), established the National Agency for the Prohibition of Trafficking in Persons (NAPTIP) as a focal agency to coordinate the investigation, arrest, and prosecution of trafficking in persons offenders.

Regrettably, despite the establishment of NAPTIP, prosecution and conviction of human trafficking offenders remain a mirage in Nigeria. According to the USDOS Annual Report (2022), the agency prosecuted only 30 cases of trafficking in persons in 2022 and obtained 13 convictions. This is against over 852 cases under its investigation. The insignificance of the of the number of prosecutions and convictions of offenders and the soaring figures of trafficked victims in Nigeria

may be a pointer to the poor criminal justice system in Nigeria, endemic weak institutional capacity to investigate, delineate human trafficking cases from other crimes, and lack of synergy among institutions in the prosecution of human traffickers. To this end, the objectives of this study are to:

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- i. Investigate effect of prompt investigation, prosecution and conviction of offenders on the fight against human trafficking in Nigeria.
- ii. Ascertain the effect of severe punishment of offenders on the fight against human trafficking in Nigeria.

2. Conceptual Framework

Human Trafficking:

A lot of controversies and debates have surrounded the definition of human trafficking. The concept of human trafficking is intertwined with those of other concepts like: migration and forced labour which makes it more complex to delineate what is human trafficking from these concepts. However, the UN Protocol to Prevent, Suppress and Punish Trafficking in Persons, Especially Women and Children (Palermo Protocol), in Article 3(a) defines human trafficking as:

...the recruitment, transportation, transfer, harbouring or receipt of persons, by means of threat or use of force or other forms of coercion, of abduction, of fraud, of deception, of the abuse of power, or of a position of vulnerability or of the giving or receiving of payments or benefits to achieve the consent of a person having control over another person, for the purpose of exploitation. Exploitation shall include, at a minimum, the exploitation of the prostitution of others or other forms of sexual exploitation, forced labour or services, slavery or practices similar to slavery, servitude or the removal of organs.

Paragraph 3(b) goes on to state:

“the consent of a victim of trafficking in persons to the intended exploitation set forth in sub paragraph (a) of this article shall be irrelevant where any of the means set forth in sub-paragraph (a) have been used.”

Paragraphs 3(c) and 3(d) qualify the definition in the case of minors:

The recruitment, transportation, transfer, harbouring or receipt of a child for the purpose of exploitation shall be considered “trafficking in persons” even if this does not involve any of the means set forth in subparagraph (a) of this article;” “Child” shall mean any person less than eighteen years of age. (UN, 2000).

According to the Protocol, minors in prostitution are considered trafficking victims; by definition they cannot have consented to be prostitutes. This is not surprising because the major elements of human trafficking are force, deception and exploitation.

Trafficking in persons Act in Nigeria also define Trafficking in persons as “all acts and attempted acts involved in the recruitment, transportation within or across Nigeria borders, purchases, sale, transfer, receipts or harboring of a person involving the use of deception, coercion or debt bondage for the purpose of placing or holding the person whether for or not in involuntary servitude (domestic, sexual or reproductive) in false or bonded or in slavery like condition”, (NAPTIP Act 2003). This definition goes beyond the Palermo Protocol definition in some respects. The inclusion of the phrase “... attempted acts...” makes it easier to prosecute offenders who are caught in the act of trafficking without having completed the transaction. The Act also takes an innovative step in criminalizing commercial carriers who transport potential trafficked victims with knowledge of the trafficking transaction.

From the afore definitions it is obvious that there are three elements that are involved in trafficking. As observed by UN –GIFT (2009), Osimen et al (2018) and USAID (2013) these elements include:

- i. The act (what is done): The operational concept of movement and transportation for example recruitment, transportation, transfer, harboring or receipt of persons.

- ii. The means (how is it done): This means the intervention of an intermediary. Most often the means is present before the act could take place namely threat or use of force, coercion, abduction, fraud, deception, abuse of power, of vulnerability or giving payments or benefits of a person in control of the victim.
- iii. An exploitative purpose (why it is done): This includes, at a minimum, the exploitation of the prostitution of others or other forms of sexual exploitation, forced labour or services, slavery or practices similar to slavery, servitude or the removal of organs.

Prosecution

Article 5 of the Palermo protocol resolved for state parties to pass legislation to criminalize human trafficking and other related offences, including legislation targeting those attempting to commit an offence, participate as an accomplice and organizing or directing trafficking in persons.

Prosecuting of trafficking offenders involves enthronelement of an effective criminal justice system, that guarantee proper and swift investigation, arrest, arraignment, prosecution, conviction and sentencing of all perpetrators of human trafficking and their accomplices.

According to USDOS (2011) effective prosecution of human trafficking offenders is an indispensable element in the fight against human trafficking and deterrents for this heinous crime. Amongst the 3ps in the Palermo protocol, prosecution is cardinal in the enforcement of the anti-trafficking protocol.

According to UNODC (2009) prosecution policy in the Palermo protocol can be evaluated based on the following indicators;

- Adoption of anti- trafficking law criminalizing trafficking in human beings.
- Legislative adoption against child trafficking.
- Application of other relevant laws in prosecuting traffickers.
- Stringency of penalty.
- Level of prosecution and conviction
- Collection of crime statistics on human trafficking.

An assessment of the role of NAPTIP in prosecution will focus on the stringency of penalty and the level of prosecution and conviction as the major indicators of prosecution. (These are because it is an already established fact that Nigeria has adopted an anti- trafficking law and other relevant laws to anti-trafficking in person in Nigeria.

Human Trafficking Offenders

The common mental construct of human trafficking offenders is organized crime syndicates or unknown men who deceitfully pay for sex or trade on sex.

According to Hughes (2004) men who purchase commercial sex fuel the demand for trafficking victims and thus should be made personally responsible and accountable for their behavior that contributes to the sex trade.

Christie (1986) argues that there is a difference between an “ideal offender” and a “real life offender”. According to him “the ideal offender differs from the real offender. He is a dangerous man coming from far away. He is a human being close to not being one ...”

Christie (1986) argues further that an “ideal offender is a distant being, the more foreign, the better, the less humane also the better, therefore, the “ideal offender “is over simplified and restricted to only monsters and hardened criminal belonging to organized crime groups. From the mental construction, given an “ideal offender” is someone who is a member of an organized criminal group and who exploits the victim very severely. The offender has deceived the victims into prostitution, use the victim and is not in personal relationship with the victim (Viuhko 2017).

This stereotype of traffickers appears on one side. The real-life trafficking offenders differ from the ideal construct. According to Weitsar (2014) traffickers are not a mono-lithic group and there is as many varieties among traffickers as there is in respect of the circumstances of their victims and that there is no standard profile of traffickers. Surtees (2008) notes that traffickers are far more diverse than what is often presented in the media and information companies. The recruiters, brokers, document processors, transporters, controllers, exploiters etc. are not always sufficiently captured as traffickers.

According to Christie (1986) the majority of offenders are “like us” and most violent offenders are in reality not so real either, most are known by the victims, many are intimately close to him or her.

According to the UNOHCHR’S recommended principles and guidelines on human rights and human trafficking, human traffic offenders are the recruiters, transporters, those who exercise control over trafficked reasons, those who transfer and or maintain trafficked persons in exploitative situations, those involved in related crimes and those who profit either directly or indirectly from trafficking, its component act and related offences. Although this definition seems comprehensive and robust, it makes identification of a real traffic offender complicated and complex. The chain on the crime of human trafficking is expansive and includes many who may not have real knowledge of the criminal activity and intent trading in human beings. For instance, a recruiter or transporter may not always be a trafficker but a regular transporter on his /her normal daily business activity, yet the exploiter who maybe the real trafficker is also a lot more other thing. As argued by Christie (1986), they may be people we know, family, friends or members of organized criminal gang.

According to Surtees (2014) there are also actors on the periphery of trafficking who may (or may not) be categorized as traffickers for example, lawyers, tax consultants, financiers or investors, accountants, employment agencies, procurers or recruiters, document forgers, guides or travel champions, visa/passport/border officials, corrupt public officials, taxi drivers, railway/bus authorities and employees, labor contractors, nightclub owners, restaurant owners, brothel operators owners and managers of set establishment etc. These categories are accessories and potential traffickers but at times very difficult to determine their intents to establish a prima fascia case of trafficking in person.

Prosecution of Offenders by NAPTIP

As the focal agency responsible for coordinating the fight against trafficking in persons, the TIPPLEA established a specialized department in NAPTIP which is responsible for the prosecution of trafficking offenders. Section II of the Act established the legal and prosecution department. Section 12 sub (2) provides the responsibility of the department to include among others to be:

- i. Responsibility for the prosecuting of offenders under the Act. The Act specifically placed the responsibility of prosecuting and act considered to be trafficking in person on the legal and prosecuting department of the agency.
- ii. The department is also empowered by the Act to provide support and legal assistance to the Agency and other department whenever it is required.

In order to ensure prosecution of offenders and conduct proceedings as may be necessary towards the recovery of any asset or property confiscated, frozen or for forfeited, the legal and prosecution department rely on its in-house legal practitioners to prosecute trafficking cases. The TIPPLEA also provided in section 14 to 35 the penalties for various offences considered in the Act as trafficking in persons and prescribed punishment ranging from N200,000 to N10,000,000 and jail terms of 6 months -5 years. Apart from the penalties the court impose on the offenders, In any trial of offence under the Act, the court is empowered notwithstanding to the contrary in any other enactment to adopt any legitimate measures that it may deem necessary to avoid unnecessary delay and abuse in the conduct of court proceedings.

TIPPLEA confers jurisdiction to try and punish all offences established under the Act on the High Court. This implies that it is the High Court that is empowered to impose the penalties provided for in the Act notwithstanding to the contrary in any other enactment. To prosecute trafficking cases in the high Courts, the legal and prosecution department has the responsibility to initiate or file for charges in the High Court. Therefore, offenders of trafficking in persons can be arraigned in any High Court.

As a criminal offence, the procedures for trials of offenders are subject to the procedures provided in the criminal procedure's Act. The constitution also confers on the Attorney – General of the federation responsible for prosecution of crimes (Sect. 174) regardless of this, the legal & prosecution department in the Agency is given responsibility for the day-to-day prosecution of trafficking offenders.

In prosecuting cases of trafficking in persons, the prosecution is expected to reasonably provide sufficient evidence to justify the institution of a charge. To achieve this, the prosecution relies

sufficiently on the evidence obtained by the investigation department of the Agency, the police, immigration service and other collaborating agencies and the victims of trafficking. The prosecutor is also expected to ensure that the legal right of the suspect is preserved in the process of trial.

3. Review of Empirical Literature

Goehrung (2019), Evaluated the Criminal Justice Approach to Human Trafficking in Taiwan. The study aimed to determine if with the massive expenditures, and a growing web of national and international laws, there is evidence suggesting that global rates of human trafficking have decreased. The study evaluates Taiwan's efforts to implement the criminal justice model by examining prosecution and sentencing data for 1,342 human trafficking apprehensions and 2,908 criminal prosecutions from 2009 to 2018. The study disaggregated the data to the individual case level by assigning a random case id to each, before running a series of descriptive analyses to gain a better sense of overall trends in apprehensions and conviction rates broken down by apprehending agencies, type of trafficking, and case outcomes. Findings from the study indicate that low conviction rates, the NIA data analyzed indicates that punishments for human trafficking tended to be minimal and are likely insufficient to effectively dissuade human traffickers. Of the small portion of those actually convicted under human trafficking laws, only 23.7% received more than a year in prison, and only 2.1% in total received sentences greater than 5 years. Findings from the study also shows low conviction rates, relatively minor punishments, and an overrepresentation of foreign sex trafficking victims indicates that the criminal justice approach may have limited efficacy in addressing other forms of trafficking. The criminal justice approach appears moderately effective in the most visible forms of trafficking, such as sex trafficking of foreigners and minors, but less visible and ultimately more prevalent forms, such as labor trafficking go largely unpunished.

Frank and Simmons (2013) examined National Law Enforcement in a Globalized World with focus on Human Trafficking. The study formulates three major hypotheses about the effects of law enforcement on human trafficking: (i) criminalization may have no effect on trafficking; (ii) criminalization may reduce human trafficking, and/or (ii) criminalization may divert human trafficking from one jurisdiction to another, as traffickers seek the path of least resistance toward

profiting from the exploitation of potential workers. To test these hypotheses, they developed a unique time series dataset that documents trafficking “corridors:” dyads of states between which human trafficking has credibly been observed and reported in the annual United States Trafficking in Persons Reports. Findings from the study shows, a reduction of trafficking within corridors where enforcement has been strengthened, but also diversion of trafficking towards contiguous neighbours of the enforcers. This is important because it suggests the enforcement of criminal law can have transnational negative externalities unless it is approached in a coordinated.

Dusek (2014), investigated the effects of a shorter criminal procedure on crime rates, the study focused on the impacts of a criminal procedure reform in the Czech Republic that allowed certain less serious offenses to be prosecuted via a simplified (fast-track or prompt) procedure. The empirical work uses statistical records from the Police of the Czech Republic and the Ministry of Justice, aggregated at the level of district, year, and offense type. There are 79 police districts each with a population of about 125,000 on average. The dataset covers three years before the reform (1999–2001) and seven years afterwards (2002–2008). It contains the number of cases that passed through individual stages of the criminal procedure, starting with the number of offenses reported to the police, the number of cases in which the suspect was identified, the number of prosecutions carried by the conventional and fast-track procedure, etc. Findings deduced from regressions analysis provide very strong evidence that a reduction in case duration led to an increase in the number of driving-related offenses that are most often discovered via police enforcement activity. Such an increase can be best explained by a substantial reallocation of police effort towards pursuing driving-related offenses, which the fast-track allowed to be “processed” at very low cost. The reallocation effect clearly dominates any deterrent effect. On the other hand, the results provide rather meagre evidence of any deterrent effect of shorter duration on ordinary, victim-reported offenses. Only the reduced form specification detected a statistically significant deterrent effect on burglary and embezzlement.

Mourtgos and Adams (2019) examined prosecutorial decisions that affect the certainty, celerity, and severity of punishment at the county level in the state of Florida. Leveraging a unique data set, they investigated the effect of the rate at which prosecuting agencies within each county filed

formal charges against offenders (certainty), the swiftness of criminal case resolution (celerity), and the rate at which cases were pled to less severe punishments (severity). They test the effect of those covariates on aggregate county-level crime rates over a 5-year period. They find that prosecutors' effect on the certainty and celerity of punishment was associated with lower levels of crime, whereas their effect on the severity of punishment was not. Together, these findings highlight the role of the prosecutor in shaping the general deterrent environment within a county.

A study by Bailey and Smith (1973) investigated Severity and Certainty of punishment, the study aimed to examine the relationship between the severity and certainty of punishment for the major index crimes in United States between 1950 and 1964. The study used 46 states in the United States as its population of study and used a longitudinal study of three periods. Certainty of punishment measure used in the investigation consisted of the number of admissions to state prisons for each of the index offenses divided by the number of such crimes reported to the police. The severity of crime was also mismeasured by the median number of months served in prison by offenders. The data were obtained from statistics published by the Federal Bureau of Prisons for 1951, 1960, and 1964. Data processing in the investigation consisted of two phases. First, correlation coefficients were computed between estimates of the severity and certainty of punishment, for all offenses, for each of the three time periods. Second, correlations were computed between changes in the levels of severity and certainty of punishment, for each offense, for corresponding time periods. The measure of association used in the analysis was the Pearson product moment correlation (r). Findings from the study indicated a substantial inverse relationship between the severity and certainty of punishment. Analysis also showed a substantial inverse relationship between changes in the levels of severity and certainty of punishment.

Gibbs (1968) examined the relationship between the severity and certainty of punishment and homicide rates for the states in USA. He hypothesized that the more certain and severe the penalties for homicide in a state, the lower the state's homicide rate would be. Estimates of the severity and certainty of punishment and offense rates were constructed from official police and prisoner statistics. Examination of these data revealed the relationship between severity and certainty of punishment and offense rates to be in the hypothesized inverse direction ($r = .25$ and $r = -.48$,

respectively), with the larger coefficient between certainty and rate entirely consistent with the position taken by practically every advocate of deterrence theory. In addition, Gibbs also concludes that the combined effects of the severity and certainty of punishment are additive in their effect on rates as deterrence theory would predict.

With regards to effectiveness of NAPTIP in prosecuting human trafficking, USAID (2005) examined Nigeria Anti-Trafficking Assessment. The study was aimed at; assessing the capacity of NAPTIP, including its ability to carry out its mandate, assessing the capacity of NAPTIP and key partner entities, including immigration authorities and police anti-trafficking units, to document and track investigations and prosecutions of alleged perpetrators of trafficking in persons, assessing the current status and operations of the Lagos shelter to determine the appropriate level of support USAID can provide to help sustain its operation and developing an inventory of efforts of other donor and local organizations to address TIP. The methodology used to conduct the assessment included literature review of relevant studies, reports, news articles, and other information on trafficking in persons in Nigeria and extensive interviews with stakeholders. The research team interviewed more than 40 persons involved in anti-trafficking including government agencies, police officials, immigration officials, NGOs, and IOs. The team travelled within Abuja, and to Lagos and Benin City, during the assessment and also interviewed the head of the immigration anti-trafficking unit from Kano. Findings from the study show that; NAPTIP has well-trained and motivated personnel who should be able to handle the tasks assigned to them given sufficient levels of support. NAPTIP is in a nascent stage, still organizing its operations and developing communications systems with partner agencies. It now employs 230 employees in the headquarters, zonal offices, and the two shelters in Lagos and Benin City. The costs of lengthy investigations and prosecutions and the lack of funding for necessary equipment hampered NAPTIP's ability to prosecute its cases. The study recommended; to increase NAPTIP's institutional capacity as well as its ability to investigate and prosecute, to Improved coordination of investigative activities among various agencies and led by NAPTIP, Development of an operational plan/MOU with police, immigration, and state ministries of justice, clearly defining roles and responsibilities, Specialized TIP and IT training for prosecutors, police, investigators,

immigration officials and judges, including the development of specialized operations manuals for law enforcement and “bench books” for judges, Appropriate equipment for communications, surveillance and data collection (i.e., computers, generators, multi-band radios, V-Sat.) A top priority should be building the institutional capacity of NAPTIP so that it can assume its role as coordinator of all TIP related activities in the country. Specifically, NAPTIP needs management and advocacy training.

Existing empirical studies on the impact of prosecution on the rate of crime or human trafficking has largely been carried out with the use of secondary data to measure the rate of conviction on the rate of crime. These may not provide an accurate measurement of the effect of conviction or enforcement of law on the rate of crime or trafficking in persons. This is because there could be other intervening variables responsible for increase or decrease in crime rate during the period under investigation. There may be shortcomings in the Panel data used in previous studies due to misrepresentation of information or non-availability of information. Again, there is no available literature on the study of the impact of prosecution on trafficking rate in Nigeria. This current study therefore intends to close this gap by adopting an opinion survey study to collect primary data from key stakeholders in the fight against human trafficking in Nigeria. The survey data will provide a reliable, usable, primary data to objectively determine the impact of prompt prosecution of offenders on the fight against trafficking in persons in Nigeria.

4. Theoretical Framework

This study anchored on the criminal deterrent theory which is based on the work of Beccaria (1872), Bentham (1781) and Hobbs (1651). Their work led to a theory of criminal deterrence involving a three-pronged approach in which certainty, celerity, and severity of punishment work together to increase the cost of an action so that a rational person will determine that the cost outweighs the benefit.

Certainty applies to the likelihood of being caught. The threat of severe punishment is not effective if there is no possibility of ever being caught.

Celerity applies to the speed of a consequence. A punishment imposed immediately after an offense is more effective than one that is imposed years after the offense.

Severity of punishment is a necessary component since a rational person might commit a crime that brings a benefit even if punishment is swift and sure when the punishment is insignificant. In addition, punishment serves as an example to others in society so that everyone is aware that a certain action is unacceptable.

5. Methodology

A causal research design was adopted for the study for the purpose of effectively measuring the cause-and-effect relationship existing between specified study variables. This was determined to be the most suited approach, given the specificity of the research direction, in line with objectives and formulated hypotheses. Using quantitative techniques, the study aimed at determining the effectiveness of the prosecution of human trafficking offenders by NAPTIP in combating human trafficking, with specific focus on: – prompt trial of offenders and severity of punishment for offenders. The data was collected through the distribution questionnaire. The nature of the questionnaire used for this study was a five-point Likert-scale, ranging from “strongly agree” to “strongly disagree” (5 = ‘Strongly Agree’, 4 = ‘Agree’, 3 = ‘Undecided’, 2 = ‘Disagree’ and 1 = ‘Strongly Disagree’). A total of 141 questionnaires were distributed to selected department in NAPTIP and selected NGOs and 129 were considered to be correctly filled. To test the formulated hypotheses for the study, multiple regression analysis was adopted in line with the causal approach employed by the study.

6. Data Analysis

Table 1: Biographical Characteristics of Respondents

	Response	Frequency	Percentage
<i>Sex</i>	Male	55	42.6%
	Female	74	57.4%
<i>Age</i>	21 – 30 years	45	34.9%
	31 – 40 years	38	29.5%
	41 and above	46	35.7%

<i>Marital Status</i>	Married	63	48.8%
	Single	38	29.5%
	Divorced	15	11.6%
	Widow/Widower	13	10.1%
<i>Educational Qualification</i>	Diploma/NCE	35	27.1%
	Degree/HND	79	61.2%
	Masters and above	15	11.6%
<i>Work Experience</i>	1-5 years	28	21.7%
	6-10 years	35	27.1%
	11-20 years	41	31.8%
	20-35 years	25	19.4%

Source: *Field Survey, 2024.*

Data collected for the study was in two main forms. The first comprised biographical information of respondents including their age, educational qualification and number of years of working experience. Collected data on sex, as presented in table 1, indicated that out of 129 respondents, 55 (42.6%) were male, while 74 (57.4%) are female. This distribution suggests a slightly higher participation of females in the survey. However, the distribution of age groups showed that 34.9% of respondents were aged 21-30 years, 29.5% were aged 31-40 years, and 35.7% were 41 years and above. This indicated a relatively balanced representation across different age brackets.

Furthermore, 48.8% indicated marriage, 29.5% reported to be single, 11.6% stated that they were divorced, while 10.1% were widow/widowers. The majority of being married indicates a significant proportion of the population with family responsibilities. The distribution of educational qualifications showed that most of the respondents (61.2%) had a Degree/HND as their highest level of educational attainment. Of the others, while 27.1% were Diploma/NCE holders, 11.6% had, at least, a master's degree. Regarding work experience, 21.7% of the respondents indicated to have 1-5 years of experience, 27.1% indicated that they had 6-10 years, 31.8% reported to have been working for the duration of 11-20 years, while 19.4% reported that they had 20-35 years. The distribution shows a relatively balanced representation across different experience levels.

Table 2: Effect of prompt Prosecution of human trafficking offender on the fight against trafficking in persons.

Items	SA	A	UD	D	SD
Are you aware of any human trafficking cases that have been prosecuted successfully?	35 (27.1%)	30 (23.3%)	25 (19.4%)	20 (15.5%)	19 (14.7%)
Do you believe that the arrest and prosecution of human trafficking offenders is carried out promptly in Nigeria?	25 (19.4%)	35 (27.1%)	15 (11.6%)	30 (23.3%)	24 (18.6%)
Speedy arrest of human trafficking offenders is crucial in deterring future crimes of human trafficking in Nigeria?	30 (23.3%)	40 (31.0%)	20 (15.5%)	14 (10.9%)	25 (19.4%)
Prompt prosecution and conviction of human trafficking offenders can reduce the rate of human trafficking in Nigeria?	40 (31.0%)	30 (23.3%)	20 (15.5%)	14 (10.9%)	25 (19.4%)
Do you think that quicker prosecution alone is enough to significantly reduce the rate of human trafficking in Nigeria?	15 (11.6%)	30 (23.3%)	25 (19.4%)	35 (27.1%)	24 (18.6%)

Source: *Field Survey, 2024.*

Table 2 indicates prompt prosecution and conviction of human traffickers on the fight against trafficking in persons. Based on responses obtained, 27.1% of respondents strongly agreed that they are aware of human trafficking cases that have been prosecuted successfully and promptly and 23.3% also agreed that they are aware. However, 15.5% of respondents disagreed, while 14.7% strongly disagreed. This was generally indicative of awareness about prosecution of offenders by NAPTIP. On the other hand, 19.4% strongly agreed that arrest and prosecution of human trafficking offenders is carried out promptly in Nigeria. This was a view by 27.1% of respondents who were also in agreement with the statement. However, 23.3% respondents disagreed, 18.6% strongly disagreed, suggesting a marginal agreement about the awareness of prosecution of offenders by NAPTIP. On the effect of speedy arrest of human trafficking offenders being crucial in deterring future crimes of human trafficking in Nigeria, 23.3% of respondents strongly felt that

speedy arrest of human trafficking offenders being crucial in deterring future crimes of human trafficking in Nigeria, while 31.0% were in agreement. However, 10.9% were in disagreement, and 19.4%, in strongly disagreement.

In the area of prompt prosecution and conviction of human trafficking offenders in reducing the rate of human trafficking in Nigeria, 31% were in strong agreement that the court do not grant application for stay of proceeding on human trafficking cases, while 23.3% agreed that this was so. However, 10% of respondents were in disagreement, as supported by 19.4% who indicated that they strongly disagreed, suggesting that prompt prosecution and conviction of human trafficking offenders can actually reduce the rate of human trafficking in Nigeria. Furthermore, 11.6% were in strong agreement that quicker prosecution alone is enough to significantly reduce the rate of human trafficking in Nigeria, while 23.3% expressed agreement. However, 27.1% of respondents disagreed, and 18.6% were in strong disagreement, indicating that apart from prosecution, other factors such as economic situation, cultural reorientation and strict border control can reduce the rate of human trafficking.

Table 3: Effect of severe punishment of human trafficking offenders on the fight against trafficking in persons in Nigeria.

Severe penalties for human trafficking will reduce the incidence of human trafficking in Nigeria?	25 (19.4%)	35 (27.1%)	20 (15.5%)	30 (23.3%)	19 (14.7%)
The current legal framework for prosecuting human trafficking cases is adequate to deter trafficking in Nigeria?	20 (15.5%)	30 (23.3%)	25 (19.4%)	35 (27.1%)	19 (14.7%)
Do you think increasing the severity of punishment for human trafficking offenders would affect the rate of human trafficking in Nigeria?	35 (27.1%)	30 (23.3%)	25 (19.4%)	15 (11.6%)	24 (18.6%)
Do you believe that severe punishments would encourage potential victims in reporting cases of human trafficking?	30 (23.3%)	40 (31.0%)	20 (15.5%)	25 (19.4%)	14 (10.9%)

Do you think the public is aware of the laws and punishments related to human trafficking?	15 (11.6%)	30 (23.3%)	25 (19.4%)	35 (27.1%)	24 (18.6%)
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Source: *Field Survey, 2024.*

As can also be seen from the information contained in table 4, when asked, 19.4% of the study respondents strongly agreed that severe penalties for human trafficking will reduce the incidence of human trafficking in Nigeria and agreed by 27.1%. However, 23.3% of respondents disagreed, as substantiated with 14.7% of collected strongly disagreed responses. Furthermore, 15.5% of respondents expressed strong agreement that the current legal framework for prosecuting human trafficking cases is adequate to deter trafficking in Nigeria, as agreed by 23.3% of the sample. However, 27.1% of respondents were in disagreement, and 14.7% strongly disagreed, indicating doubts about the adequacy of the current legal framework for prosecuting human trafficking cases to adequately deter trafficking in Nigeria. As part of the survey conducted, respondents were asked to indicate their views if increasing the severity of punishment for human trafficking offenders would affect the rate of human trafficking in Nigeria. Their responses, as contained in table 4 indicate that, 23.3% and 31.0% of respondents strongly agreed and agreed, respectively, that increasing the severity of punishment for human trafficking offenders would affect the rate of human trafficking in Nigeria. However, 19.4% of respondents disagreed, while 10.9% were in strong disagreement, indicating that increasing the severity of punishment for human trafficking offenders would affect the rate of human trafficking in Nigeria. In terms of potential victims reporting cases of human trafficking, 23.3% of respondents strongly agreed that severe punishments would encourage potential victims to report cases of human trafficking appropriate authority for prosecution, while 31.0% agreed. However, 19.4% of respondents disagreed, while 10.9% were in strong disagreement, indicating that severe punishments would encourage potential victims to report cases of human trafficking. On the public awareness of consequences of trafficking in persons, 11.6% respondents agreed that the public is aware of the laws and punishments related to human trafficking while 23.3% strongly agreed. However, 27.1% disagreed and 18.6% strongly disagreed. This indicate that most members of the public are not aware of the punishment associated with the crime of human trafficking.

7. Test of Hypothesis

In examining the specified causal relationship among variables, multiple regression analysis was applied to the collected survey data. This was essential in evaluating the effect of prosecution (promptness in prosecution and severity of punishment) on the fight against human trafficking in Nigeria. Table 5 shows Coefficient of Determination statistics for the estimated model. The adjusted R² statistic, as can be seen, showed a high explanatory ability of the estimated model. R² measures the proportion of variance in the dependent variable (Human Trafficking Rate) that is explained by the independent variables. In this case, adjusted R-squared was determined to be 0.588, indicating that approximately 59% of the variance in Human Trafficking Rate was explained by the independent variables.

Table 5: Model Summary

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square
0.778	0.605	0.588

Source: SPSS Output.

Model fitness was evaluated using the F statistic. Table 6 summaries the result of the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) estimation that was carried out in the course of the study to test how well the estimated regression model fitted the collected survey data. It can be seen, from the result that the model did fit the data well, given a significant F coefficient (47.396, $p < 0.05$).

Table 6: ANOVA Result

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	124.560	4	47.610	47.396	0.000
Residual	190.440	124	1.005		
Total	315.000	128			

Source: SPSS Output.

Regression coefficients obtained, and shown in table 6, indicated the estimated change in the dependent variable (Human Trafficking Rate) for a one-unit change in the independent variable, holding other variables constant. These estimated coefficients for all modelled components of

effective prosecution were found to be negatively signed. Furthermore, estimated collinearity statistics provided Tolerance and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) information for the fitted model. VIF for all the variables were determined to be far less than 5; in fact, most of them were not much greater than 1. This implied that there was no significant multi-collinearity among the independent variables.

Table 5: Estimated Regression Coefficients

	Unstandardized Coefficients		T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	φ	Std. Error			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	0.012	0.032	32.181	0.013		
PPO	-0.354	0.011	10.523	0.000	0.958	1.044
SOP	-0.532	0.045	18.739	0.000	0.605	1.653

Source: SPSS Output.

Test of Hypothesis

Test of Hypothesis H01: Prompt arrest and prosecution of human trafficking offenders by NAPTIP has no significant effect on the fight against human trafficking in Nigeria.

The results of the analysis carried out indicated a negative and statistically significant effect of prompt prosecution of human trafficking offenders (POP) on the fight against human trafficking in Nigeria. This was confirmed by a negatively signed estimated coefficient, as well as a significant t and satisfactory p value (-0.354, $t = 32.181$, $p < 0.05$). The null hypothesis in this case was therefore not accepted.

H02: The severity of punishment for human trafficking offenders does not significantly affect the fight against human trafficking in Nigeria.

In testing the effect of severity of punishment on the fight against trafficking in persons, estimates were obtained for the SOP variable. Accordingly, the coefficients thereof were found to be negative and statistically significant at the 5% significant level (-0.532, $t = 18.739$, $p < 0.05$), indicating that the severity of punishment of offenders had a negative effect on the human trafficking rate. Based on this result, the null hypothesis was not accepted in this case.

Discussion of Findings

The result of findings from this study indicates that there is a significant effect of prosecution of human trafficking offenders in the fight to curb and suppress human trafficking in Nigeria. A study shows that prompt arrest, trial, and conviction of human trafficking offenders has the propensity to deter other criminals from engaging in such crimes. This study aligned with the argument by the criminal deterrent theorist that the severity of punishment will deter crime.

The findings also highlighted that the severity of punishment is an additive factor. That is, when punishments are severe and administered with promptness, maximum deterrence results. Inversely, when punishments are slight and delayed, deterrence will be minimal. This result also affirms findings from previous studies by Grasmick and Bryjack (2014) that concluded that perceived severity, at relatively high levels of perceived certainty, has a significant deterrent effect.

8. Conclusion

Prosecution of human trafficking offenders is very crucial in the crusade against trafficking in person. NAPTIP, as the focal agency in this fight, has made many strides by securing the conviction of offenders. The Agency has adopted many strategies to ensure one of its primary mandates to arrest, detain, and prosecute offenders under the TIPLEA or any other law on trafficking in persons in Nigeria is achieved. It has collaborated with other agencies, multilateral and bilateral agencies, and state parties to ensure offenders are identified with substantial evidence, proceeds from trafficking seized, and offenders that are to be extradited are repatriated or brought back to the country for prosecution.

However, a lot more needs to be done to ensure more offenders are behind bars for their heinous crimes against human persons and society. The judicial officers and prosecutors must be adequately protected from the offenders and their criminal gang to safeguard them from being attacked by the human trafficking criminal ring. Frontline law enforcement agencies, particularly

the top hierarchy of the Nigeria police force, must prevail on their subordinates to relinquish trafficking cases to NAPTIP for prompt and effective prosecution.

The agency needs a lot of funding to procure the adequate and sophisticated equipment and skills required in all the states of the federation to curtail and intercept the clandestine acts of trafficking. NAPTIP should launch a nationwide awareness campaign to educate the public about human trafficking and highlight successful prosecution cases to demonstrate the effectiveness of the legal system in combating trafficking. Awareness will also encourage local communities to monitor and report human trafficking activities to law enforcement for prompt prosecution of offenders.

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